

Expected results

- Novel food systems framework, holistic indicators & gap analysis to guide development of agri-food models.
- Modular Toolbox for Sustainable Food System Policy Modelling to support agricultural modelling capacity of EU member states.
- Assessment of potential future agri-food policy options.
- Monitoring and projecting environmental, social & economic indicators of the EU food system.
- New generation of agri-food system modellers & EU wide community of model practitioners.
- Dissemination & Stakeholder Platform bringing together food system experts and EU modellers and analysts providing them with an open access to the ACT4CAP27 Portal.
- Impact of agricultural policy analysis on performance of the EU food system fostered through a programme of engagement with key stakeholders at regional, country and EU levels.
- ACT4CAP27 Interactive Roadmap with transition narratives and pathways to achieve medium- to long-term sustainable food systems in the EU.

Partners

Project coordination

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Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

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Challenges in Policy Impact Assessment

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) stands as the European Union's cornerstone for supporting agriculture, ensuring food security, and driving rural development. Aligned with the objectives of the European Green Deal, encompassing the Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategy, the CAP plays a pivotal role in reshaping Europe's agri-food systems for sustainability.

In the evolving landscape of the European Green Deal, existing quantitative modeling tools face a monumental challenge in comprehensively addressing all components of the policy. The need to align with the ambitious goals of the Green Deal, including sustainability and biodiversity, demands a significant enhancement in thematic coverage.

Support for evidence-based EU agri-food policies post-2027

ACT4CAP27 aims to enhance analytical capabilities, tools, and collaborative technical infrastructure within the policy modelling community.

The project adopts a comprehensive food system (FS) approach, focusing on building analytical capacity for the quantitative assessment of the impacts of upcoming agri-food policies on the economic, social (including health), environmental, and climate sustainability of food systems.

Through the identification of synergies, trade-offs, and linkages, the project enhances the effectiveness and efficiency of regulatory pathways, particularly in the context of ongoing shocks and disruptions across Europe and globally.

Specific objectives

- **DESIGNING** a conceptual data and modelling framework to operationalize and better understand the determinants and indicators for an improved EU food system performance and **ASSESSING** policy impact.
- Developing an enhanced modular **MODELLING** Toolbox to quantify the transition to a sustainable EU food system and its contribution to societal goals.
- **SAFEGUARDING** the uptake and update of the integrated and modular toolbox and community building.
- **PLATFORM** for stakeholder interaction and dialogues – at different stages of the project

